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Putative immunomodulatory properties of Parp1/2 inhibitors.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

PARP1 and PARP2 reside upstream of the tyrosine kinases that conduct growth factor signaling based on which the minimal circuitry of an 'addicted' cancer cell is thought to arise. Immunoregulatory effects of interference with cyclic nucleotide signaling pathways and related systems in cancer cells is not completely understood. We describe here putative immunoregulatory properties associated with Parp1/2 inhibition in cancer cells.

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Results

We measured total transcription in cells following pharmacologic inhibition of Parp1/2 with tazoparib or olaparib.

- a. Il6 induction was a primary consequence of Parp1/2 pharmacologic inhibition.
- b. Selective activation of Ifitm10 in cells following Parpi.
 - i. Silencing of the Ifit family
- c. System-wide nucleotide enzymatic silencing resulting from Parp1/2 inhibition.
- d. Parp1/2 inhibition results in CCR10 silencing.
- e. Induction of HLA-H with repression of HLA-J in cells treated with a small molecular inhibitor of Parp1/2.
 - i. Repression of histocompatibility marker

Discussion

We described here for the first time putative immunomodulatory properties associated with Parp1/2 inhibition in human cells.

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Methods

We used identified transcriptomic data (GSE221233) and RNA-sequencing for this study.

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Citations

1. Stewart, R.A., Pilié, P.G. and Yap, T.A., 2018. Development of PARP and immune-checkpoint inhibitor combinations. *Cancer research*, 78(24), pp.6717-6725.
2. Thawani, R. and Kummar, S., 2023. Combining PARP inhibitor with immunotherapy—does the promise of preclinical data translate to clinic?. *JAMA oncology*, 9(1), pp.25-27.